

[Biomarker Analytical Laboratories](#)

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**Title: SOP for Relative quantification of protein
neuromarkers in cell samples using UHPLC/SRM-MS**

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Summary

Neurodifferentiation is a process in which neural stem cells or neuroepithelial cells specialize into radial glial cells, bipolar-shaped neural progenitor cells capable of producing neurons, astrocytes, and oligodendrocytes. This process is accompanied by the expression of specific biomarkers. We developed a multiplex selected reaction monitoring (SRM)-MS assay that enables the relative quantification of 17 cell-specific protein neuromarkers, such as neuronal migration protein doublecortin (DCX), vimentin (VIM), microtubule-associated protein 2 (MAP2), or myelin basic protein (MBP) plus one constitutively expressed housekeeping protein (GAPDH).

Table 1: Analyzed proteins and the targeted peptides

Protein name	Accession number	Gene name	Target peptide
Transcription factor SOX-2	P48431	SOX2	LLSETEK APCQAGDLR
Nestin	P48681	NES	VGLNAQAACAPR ALEEQNELLSAELGGLR
Tubulin beta-3 chain	Q13509	TUBB3	ISVYYNEASSHK MSSTFIGNSTAIQELFK
Neuronal migration protein doublecortin	O43602	DCX	SLSDNINLPQGVR YIYTIDGSR GIVYAVSSDR
Paired box protein Pax-6	P26367	PAX6	YYETGSIRPR THYPDVFAR TSFTQEQIEALEK IQVWFSNR
Microtubule-associated protein 2	P11137	MAP2	LINQPLPDLK LASVSADAEVAR

			IVQVVTAEAVVLK DLATDLSLIEVK EEFVETCPSEHK
Choline O-acetyltransferase	P28329	CHAT	EVRPACFLQSGGR LSEGDLFTQLR LVPTYESASIR
Synaptophysin	P08247	SYP	EPLGFVK MATDPENIIK ETGWAAAPFLR LHQVYFDAPTCR
Cadherin-2	P19022	CDH2	MFVLTVAENQVPLAK DWVIPPINLPENSR ESAEVEEIVFPR VQYESSEPADFK
Glial fibrillary acidic protein	P14136	GFAP	LLQTGTEDQGK ALAAELNQLR HLQEYQDLLNVK
Fatty acid binding protein 7	O15540	FABP7	ALGVGFATR SVVSLDGDK LTNSQNFDEYMK
Vimentin	P08670	VIM	EEAENTLQSFR DNLAEDIMR LGDLYEEEMR
Protein S100-B	P04271	S100B	AMVALIDVFHQYSGR ELINNELSHFLEEIK
Neurofilament light polypeptide	P07196	NEFL	FTVLTESAAK ALYEQEIR TLEIEACR IDSLMDEISFLK
Neurofilament medium polypeptide	P07197	NEFM	QASHAQLGDAYDQEIR SIELESVR EEAVAEEVVTITK
Oligodendrocyte transcription factor 2	Q13516	OLIG2	MHDLNIAMDGLR YLATASTMDHAR DTGILDSIGR GVDAQGTLSK
Myelin basic protein	P02686	MBP	LVINGNPITIFQER LISWYDNEFGYSNR GALQNIIPASTGAAK

Safety information

- Cell samples are classified as biohazardous material & thus all items in contact (e.g. pipette tips, vials) should be disposed of appropriately.

Overview of reagents

- Ammonium bicarbonate buffer (ABB)
- N-dodecyl- β -D-maltoside (DDM)
- Dithiothreitol (DTT)
- Iodoacetamide (IAA)
- Trypsin gold
- Acetic acid
- Acetonitrile (ACN) LC-MS grade
- Formic acid (FA) LC-MS grade
- MiliQ water

Equipment

- 10 μ L, 200 μ L, and 1000 μ L pipette
- 10 μ L, 100 μ L, and 300 μ L multichannel pipette
- 1200 μ L automatic multichannel pipette
- Orbital shaker incubator
- Thermo shaker for deep well plates
- Centrifugal evaporator
- Mini vortex or vortex for 96-well plates
- Centrifuge MiniSpin
- pH meter
- SPE manifold with pump
- Homogenizator
- Sonicator

LC-MS equipment

- Vanquish Neo UHPLC coupled with TSQ Altis Plus
- Easy-Spray Pep Map column (RSLC C18, 2 μm , 15cmX150 μm , ES906)

Consumables & glassware

- 50 mL Falcon screw cap plastic vials
- 700 μL 96-well plates with silicone sealing
- 10 μL , 200 μL , 300 μL , 1000 μL , and 1200 μL tips
- 500 μL and 1.5 ml Eppendorf tubes
- 250 μL Polypropylen vials with screw lid
- 96 well plate SPE HLB PRIME 30 mg
- Glass beads for homogenization
- BCA Protein Assay Kit

Reagents for standard and sample preparation

Protein extraction buffer

- 100 mM ABB: dissolve 80 mg of ammonium bicarbonate in 10 mL of MiliQ water
- 1% DDM buffer: dissolve 20 mg of DDM in 2 ml of ABB
- 0.1 % DDM buffer: mix 100 μL of 1% DDM buffer with 900 μl ABB

Reduction and alkylation solutions

- 200 mM DTT: dissolve 30.8 mg in 1 mL of ABB buffer.
- 400 mM IAA: dissolve 74 mg in 1 mL of ABB buffer.

Trypsin solution

- As described in trypsin standard manual, dissolve 100 µg lyophilized trypsin in 100 µL of 50 mM acetic acid.

SPE solutions

- 2% FA (pH<3)
- 0.1% FA
- 50% ACN with 0.1%FA
- 5% ACN with 0.1% FA

Standard preparation

- To prepare 500 µl of SIL ST_L 3w3 mixture, pipette defined volume of 100 µM peptide SIL ST_L 3w3 standard listed in **Table 2** and 294 µL of 20% ACN with 0.1% DDM buffer (in 100 mM ABB).

Table 2: SIL mixture volumes and concentrations. Stable isotope-labeled arginine or lysine is marked in bold.

Protein	SIL 3w3 peptide sequence	Peptide concentration in sample [nM]	Peptide concentration in ST_L mixture [nM]	Volume of 100 µM standard [µl]
SOX2	EWK-LLSETE K -RPF	5	400	2
	HSR-APCQAGDL R -DMI	5	400	2
NES	EER-VGLNAQAACAP R -CPA	5	400	2
	VK-ALEEQNELLSAELGGL R -AQ	5	400	2
TUBB3	LER-ISVYYNEASS H K-YV	30	2400	12
	LK-MSSTFIGNSTAIQEL F K-RI	30	2400	12
DCX	LTR-SLSDNINLPQGV R -YIY	5	400	2
	GVR-YIYTIDG S R-KIG	5	400	2
	YFK-GIVYAVSS D R-FRS	5	400	2
PAX6	LGR-YYETGSIR P R-AIG	5	400	2
	FER-THYPDVF A R-ERL	5	400	2
	RNR-TSFTQEIQIEAL E K-EFE	5	400	2

	EAR-IQVWFSNR-RAK	5	400	2
MAP2	QLR-LINQPLPDLK-NVK	5	400	2
	RSR-LASVSADAЕVAR-RKS	5	400	2
	SAR-IVQVVTAЕAVAVLK-GEQ	5	400	2
	VRR-DLATDLSLIEVK-LAA	5	400	2
	GAR-EEFVETCPSEHK-GVI	5	400	2
	GRR-EVRPACFLQSGGR-GD	5	400	2
CHAT	FRR-LSEGDLFTQLR-KIV	5	400	2
	HRR-LVPTYESASIR-RFQ	5	400	2
	VVK-EPLGFVK-VLQ	5	400	2
SYP	DVK-MATDPENIIK-EM	5	400	2
	VFK-ETGWAAPFLR-APPG	5	400	2
	PFR-LHQVYFDAPTCR-GGT	5	400	2
	TNR-MFVLTVAАENQVPLAK-GI	5	400	2
CDH2	QKR-DWVIPPINLPENSR-GPF	5	400	2
	SVK-ESAEVEEIVFPR-QFS	5	400	2
	KRK-VQYESSEPADFK-VDE	5	400	2
	ACR-LLQTGTEDQGK-GIQ	5	400	2
GFAP	QNK-ALAAELNQLR-AKE	5	400	2
	MAR-HLQEYQDLLNVK-LAL	5	400	2
	YMK-ALGVGFATR-QVG	5	400	2
FABP7	NCK-SVVSDGDK-LVH	5	400	2
	TWK-LTNSQNFDEYMK-ALG	5	400	2
	LQR-EEAENTLQSFR-QDV	25	2000	10
VIM	VER-DNLAEDIMR-LRE	25	2000	10
	KSR-LGDLYEEEMR-ELR	25	2000	10
	LEK-AMVALIDVFHQYSGR-EGD	5	400	2
S100B	ELK-ELINNELSHFLEEIK-EQE	5	400	2
	KSR-FTVLTESAАK-NTD	5	400	2
NEFL	RFR-ALYEQEIR-DLR	5	400	2
	KAK-TLEIEACR-GMN	5	400	2
	EKR-IDSLMDEISFLK-KVH	5	400	2
	RQK-QASHAQLGDAYDQEIR-EL	5	400	2
NEFM	QSK-SIELESVR-GTK	5	400	2
	PVK-EEAЕAVVTTIK-SVK	5	400	2
	RKR-MHDLNIAMDGLR-EVM	5	400	2
MBP	GSK-YLATASTMDHAR-HGF	5	400	2
	RHR-DTGILDSIGR-FFG	5	400	2
	GFK-GVDAQGTLSK-IFK	5	400	2
GAPDH	NGK-LVINGNPITIFQER-DPS	50	4000	20
	FVK-LISWYDNEFGYSNR-VVD	50	4000	20
	GR-GALQNIIPASTGAAK-AVG	50	4000	20

Protein extraction

1. Add 100 μL of 0.1% DDM buffer (in 100 mM ABB) to the sample and vortex properly.
2. Add a glass bead and homogenize samples (4 m/s, 15 s, four cycles with 10 s inter-time).
3. Sonicate samples for 1 min at 80 kHz.
4. Place onto the shaker and shake 2000 RPM for 10 min at room temperature.
5. Centrifuge for 1 min at 12300 RCF.
6. Transfer the extract to a new Eppendorf tube.
7. Take 8 μL of extract for total protein analysis using BCA kit (dilute 3x, i.e. 8 μL of extract and 16 μL of 0.1% DDM buffer).
8. For proteomics analysis, dilute the extract to concentration of total protein 2.5 $\mu\text{g}/10 \mu\text{L}$.
9. Take 20 μL of diluted extract (5 μg of total protein/20 μL) for target protein analysis and place into a 700 μL deep well plate.

Reduction and alkylation

10. Add 1 μL of DTT solution and incubate at 90 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 10 min in heated block.
11. Leave to cool down for 15 minutes.
12. Add 1 μL of IAA solution and incubate in dark for 30 min at room temperature.

Trypsin digestion

13. Dilute SIL ST_L 3w3 mixture 20x using 20% ACN with 0.1% DDM buffer (in 100 mM ABB).
14. Add 10 μL of diluted SIL ST_L 3w3 mixture to the sample.
15. Dilute the trypsin solution 5x using 100 mM ABB.
16. Add 2.5 μL of diluted trypsin solution to the sample.
17. Seal microplate with silicone seal.
18. Place into a heat shaker and shake at 200 RPM for 6 hours at 37 $^{\circ}\text{C}$.
19. Stop digestion adding 200 μL of 2% FA.

SPE in 96-well microplate format

20. Load sample solution into a SPE well and turn vacuum on to elute solution into waste.
21. Wash sample with 300 μ L of 0.1% FA.
22. Elute peptides with 200 μ L of 50% ACN with 0.1% FA into a 700 μ L microplate with V bottom.
23. Dry out the sample in centrifugal evaporator at 40 $^{\circ}$ C for 3h.
24. Store in freezer -20 $^{\circ}$ C or dissolve samples for UHPLC/MS analysis.
25. Dissolve in 40 μ L of 5% ACN with 0.1% FA.
26. Vortex properly.
27. Analyze using UHPLC/MS.

Vanquish NEO – TSQ Altis Plus analysis

28. Prepare Vanquish NEO – TSQ Altis Plus according to the *SOP for Preparation of Vanquish Neo UHPLC-TSQ Altis Plus for analysis*.
29. Use dSRM assay as shown in **Table 3** with Vanquish NEO – TSQ Altis Plus method setup shown in **Table 4**.
30. Inject 3 μ L of samples to the UHPLC Vanquish NEO equipped with Easy-Spray Pep Map column (RSLC C18, 2 μ m, 15cmX150 μ m, ES906) thermostated at 40 $^{\circ}$ C.
31. Start UHPLC-MS analysis sequence.
32. Check initial blanks and QC.
33. Store samples at -20 $^{\circ}$ C.

NOTE: If there are problems, stop sequence, cap/seal samples and store at -20 $^{\circ}$ C whilst troubleshooting.

Table 3. dSRM assay in analytical method

Compound	Retention Time (min)	RT Window (min)	Precursor (m/z)	Product (m/z)	Collision Energy (V)
ALAAELNQLR	7.6	2	549.82	772.43	22.8
ALAAELNQLR	7.6	2	549.82	843.47	22.8
ALAAELNQLR	7.6	2	549.82	914.51	22.8

ALAAELNQLR_SIL	7.6	2	554.82	782.44	22.8
ALAAELNQLR_SIL	7.6	2	554.82	853.48	22.8
ALAAELNQLR_SIL	7.6	2	554.82	924.51	22.8
ALEEQNELLSAELGGLR	8.5	2	614.66	402.25	17.3
ALEEQNELLSAELGGLR	8.5	2	614.66	515.33	17.3
ALEEQNELLSAELGGLR	8.5	2	614.66	802.44	17.3
ALEEQNELLSAELGGLR_SIL	8.5	2	617.99	412.25	17.3
ALEEQNELLSAELGGLR_SIL	8.5	2	617.99	525.34	17.3
ALEEQNELLSAELGGLR_SIL	8.5	2	617.99	812.45	17.3
ALGVGFATR	6.7	2	446.26	242.15	19.8
ALGVGFATR	6.7	2	446.26	551.29	19.8
ALGVGFATR	6.7	2	446.26	707.38	19.8
ALGVGFATR_SIL	6.7	2	451.26	242.15	19.8
ALGVGFATR_SIL	6.7	2	451.26	561.3	19.8
ALGVGFATR_SIL	6.7	2	451.26	717.39	19.8
ALYEQEIR	5.7	2	511.27	545.3	21.7
ALYEQEIR	5.7	2	511.27	674.35	21.7
ALYEQEIR	5.7	2	511.27	837.41	21.7
ALYEQEIR_SIL	5.7	2	516.27	555.31	21.7
ALYEQEIR_SIL	5.7	2	516.27	684.36	21.7
ALYEQEIR_SIL	5.7	2	516.27	847.42	21.7
AMVALIDVFHQYSGR	8.5	2	569.63	667.85	15.7
AMVALIDVFHQYSGR	8.5	2	569.63	703.37	15.7
AMVALIDVFHQYSGR	8.5	2	569.63	752.9	15.7
AMVALIDVFHQYSGR_SIL	8.5	2	572.96	672.85	15.7
AMVALIDVFHQYSGR_SIL	8.5	2	572.96	708.37	15.7
AMVALIDVFHQYSGR_SIL	8.5	2	572.96	757.9	15.7
APCQAGDLR	3.4	2	494.24	288.2	21.2
APCQAGDLR	3.4	2	494.24	531.29	21.2
APCQAGDLR	3.4	2	494.24	819.38	21.2
APCQAGDLR_SIL	3.4	2	499.24	298.21	21.2
APCQAGDLR_SIL	3.4	2	499.24	541.3	21.2
APCQAGDLR_SIL	3.4	2	499.24	829.39	21.2
DLATDLSLIEVK	9	2	658.87	688.42	26
DLATDLSLIEVK	9	2	658.87	1017.58	26
DLATDLSLIEVK	9	2	658.87	1088.62	26
DLATDLSLIEVK_SIL	9	2	662.88	696.44	26
DLATDLSLIEVK_SIL	9	2	662.88	1025.6	26
DLATDLSLIEVK_SIL	9	2	662.88	1096.63	26
DNLAEDIMR	8.2	2	538.76	534.27	22.5
DNLAEDIMR	8.2	2	538.76	663.31	22.5
DNLAEDIMR	8.2	2	538.76	734.35	22.5
DNLAEDIMR_SIL	8.2	2	543.76	544.28	22.5

DNLAEDIMR_SIL	8.2	2	543.76	673.32	22.5
DNLAEDIMR_SIL	8.2	2	543.76	744.36	22.5
DTGILDSIGR	8.2	2	523.78	547.28	22.1
DTGILDSIGR	8.2	2	523.78	660.37	22.1
DTGILDSIGR	8.2	2	523.78	830.47	22.1
DTGILDSIGR_SIL	8.2	2	528.78	557.29	22.1
DTGILDSIGR_SIL	8.2	2	528.78	670.38	22.1
DTGILDSIGR_SIL	8.2	2	528.78	840.48	22.1
DWVIPPINLPENSR	8.9	2	825.44	568.81	30.9
DWVIPPINLPENSR	8.9	2	825.44	602.29	30.9
DWVIPPINLPENSR	8.9	2	825.44	1136.61	30.9
DWVIPPINLPENSR_SIL	8.9	2	830.44	573.81	30.9
DWVIPPINLPENSR_SIL	8.9	2	830.44	612.3	30.9
DWVIPPINLPENSR_SIL	8.9	2	830.44	1146.61	30.9
EEAENTLQSFR	6.5	2	662.31	409.22	26.1
EEAENTLQSFR	6.5	2	662.31	537.28	26.1
EEAENTLQSFR	6.5	2	662.31	865.45	26.1
EEAENTLQSFR_SIL	6.5	2	667.32	419.23	26.1
EEAENTLQSFR_SIL	6.5	2	667.32	547.29	26.1
EEAENTLQSFR_SIL	6.5	2	667.32	875.46	26.1
EEAFAEVVTITK	7.7	2	644.85	462.29	25.6
EEAFAEVVTITK	7.7	2	644.85	660.43	25.6
EEAFAEVVTITK	7.7	2	644.85	860.51	25.6
EEAFAEVVTITK_SIL	7.7	2	648.86	470.31	25.6
EEAFAEVVTITK_SIL	7.7	2	648.86	668.44	25.6
EEAFAEVVTITK_SIL	7.7	2	648.86	868.52	25.6
EEFVETCPSEHK	4.2	2	497.89	429.69	13.1
EEFVETCPSEHK	4.2	2	497.89	494.21	13.1
EEFVETCPSEHK	4.2	2	497.89	543.75	13.1
EEFVETCPSEHK_SIL	4.2	2	500.56	433.7	13.1
EEFVETCPSEHK_SIL	4.2	2	500.56	498.22	13.1
EEFVETCPSEHK_SIL	4.2	2	500.56	547.76	13.1
ELINNELSHFLEEIK	8.9	2	609.99	679.85	17.2
ELINNELSHFLEEIK	8.9	2	609.99	736.87	17.2
ELINNELSHFLEEIK	8.9	2	609.99	793.42	17.2
ELINNELSHFLEEIK_SIL	8.9	2	612.66	683.86	17.2
ELINNELSHFLEEIK_SIL	8.9	2	612.66	740.88	17.2
ELINNELSHFLEEIK_SIL	8.9	2	612.66	797.42	17.2
EPLGFVK	6.5	2	395.23	246.18	18.3
EPLGFVK	6.5	2	395.23	450.27	18.3
EPLGFVK	6.5	2	395.23	563.36	18.3
EPLGFVK_SIL	6.5	2	399.24	254.2	18.3
EPLGFVK_SIL	6.5	2	399.24	458.29	18.3

EPLGFVK_SIL	6.5	2	399.24	571.37	18.3
ESAEVEEIVFPR	8.2	2	702.85	419.24	27.3
ESAEVEEIVFPR	8.2	2	702.85	889.48	27.3
ESAEVEEIVFPR	8.2	2	702.85	988.55	27.3
ESAEVEEIVFPR_SIL	8.2	2	707.86	429.25	27.3
ESAEVEEIVFPR_SIL	8.2	2	707.86	899.49	27.3
ESAEVEEIVFPR_SIL	8.2	2	707.86	998.56	27.3
ETGWAAPFLR	8.4	2	574.3	532.32	23.5
ETGWAAPFLR	8.4	2	574.3	603.36	23.5
ETGWAAPFLR	8.4	2	574.3	674.4	23.5
ETGWAAPFLR_SIL	8.4	2	579.3	542.33	23.5
ETGWAAPFLR_SIL	8.4	2	579.3	613.37	23.5
ETGWAAPFLR_SIL	8.4	2	579.3	684.41	23.5
EVRPACFLQSGGR	6.1	2	492.92	376.19	12.9
EVRPACFLQSGGR	6.1	2	492.92	504.25	12.9
EVRPACFLQSGGR	6.1	2	492.92	617.34	12.9
EVRPACFLQSGGR_SIL	6.1	2	496.25	386.2	12.9
EVRPACFLQSGGR_SIL	6.1	2	496.25	514.26	12.9
EVRPACFLQSGGR_SIL	6.1	2	496.25	627.35	12.9
FTVLTESAAK	6.3	2	533.79	606.31	22.4
FTVLTESAAK	6.3	2	533.79	719.39	22.4
FTVLTESAAK	6.3	2	533.79	818.46	22.4
FTVLTESAAK_SIL	6.3	2	537.8	614.32	22.4
FTVLTESAAK_SIL	6.3	2	537.8	727.41	22.4
FTVLTESAAK_SIL	6.3	2	537.8	826.48	22.4
GALQNIIPASTGAAK	7.8	2	706.4	242.15	27.4
GALQNIIPASTGAAK	7.8	2	706.4	815.46	27.4
GALQNIIPASTGAAK	7.8	2	706.4	1042.59	27.4
GALQNIIPASTGAAK_SIL	7.8	2	710.41	242.15	27.4
GALQNIIPASTGAAK_SIL	7.8	2	710.41	823.48	27.4
GALQNIIPASTGAAK_SIL	7.8	2	710.41	1050.6	27.4
GIVYAVSSDR	5.8	2	533.78	563.28	22.4
GIVYAVSSDR	5.8	2	533.78	634.32	22.4
GIVYAVSSDR	5.8	2	533.78	797.38	22.4
GIVYAVSSDR_SIL	5.8	2	538.78	573.29	22.4
GIVYAVSSDR_SIL	5.8	2	538.78	644.32	22.4
GIVYAVSSDR_SIL	5.8	2	538.78	807.39	22.4
GVDAQGTLISK	3.7	2	488.26	347.23	21
GVDAQGTLISK	3.7	2	488.26	505.3	21
GVDAQGTLISK	3.7	2	488.26	819.42	21
GVDAQGTLISK_SIL	3.7	2	492.27	355.24	21
GVDAQGTLISK_SIL	3.7	2	492.27	513.31	21
GVDAQGTLISK_SIL	3.7	2	492.27	827.44	21

HLQEYQDLLNVK	7.7	2	500.6	473.31	13.2
HLQEYQDLLNVK	7.7	2	500.6	508.25	13.2
HLQEYQDLLNVK	7.7	2	500.6	701.42	13.2
HLQEYQDLLNVK_SIL	7.7	2	503.27	481.32	13.2
HLQEYQDLLNVK_SIL	7.7	2	503.27	508.25	13.2
HLQEYQDLLNVK_SIL	7.7	2	503.27	709.43	13.2
IDSLMDEISFLK	9	2	705.86	851.45	27.4
IDSLMDEISFLK	9	2	705.86	982.49	27.4
IDSLMDEISFLK	9	2	705.86	1182.61	27.4
IDSLMDEISFLK_SIL	9	2	709.87	859.47	27.4
IDSLMDEISFLK_SIL	9	2	709.87	990.51	27.4
IDSLMDEISFLK_SIL	9	2	709.87	1190.62	27.4
IQVWFSNR	8	2	525.28	523.26	22.1
IQVWFSNR	8	2	525.28	709.34	22.1
IQVWFSNR	8	2	525.28	808.41	22.1
IQVWFSNR_SIL	8	2	530.28	533.27	22.1
IQVWFSNR_SIL	8	2	530.28	719.35	22.1
IQVWFSNR_SIL	8	2	530.28	818.42	22.1
ISVYYNEASSHK	4.4	2	466.56	549.75	12
ISVYYNEASSHK	4.4	2	466.56	599.28	12
ISVYYNEASSHK	4.4	2	466.56	642.8	12
ISVYYNEASSHK_SIL	4.4	2	469.23	553.75	12
ISVYYNEASSHK_SIL	4.4	2	469.23	603.29	12
ISVYYNEASSHK_SIL	4.4	2	469.23	646.8	12
IVQVVTAEAVAVLK	8.3	2	720.45	341.22	27.8
IVQVVTAEAVAVLK	8.3	2	720.45	901.54	27.8
IVQVVTAEAVAVLK	8.3	2	720.45	1000.6	27.8
IVQVVTAEAVAVLK_SIL	8.3	2	724.45	341.22	27.8
IVQVVTAEAVAVLK_SIL	8.3	2	724.45	909.55	27.8
IVQVVTAEAVAVLK_SIL	8.3	2	724.45	1008.62	27.8
LASVSADAEVAR	5.3	2	594.82	660.33	24.1
LASVSADAEVAR	5.3	2	594.82	731.37	24.1
LASVSADAEVAR	5.3	2	594.82	818.4	24.1
LASVSADAEVAR_SIL	5.3	2	599.82	670.34	24.1
LASVSADAEVAR_SIL	5.3	2	599.82	741.38	24.1
LASVSADAEVAR_SIL	5.3	2	599.82	828.41	24.1
LGDLYEEEMR	7.5	2	627.79	564.25	25.1
LGDLYEEEMR	7.5	2	627.79	693.29	25.1
LGDLYEEEMR	7.5	2	627.79	856.35	25.1
LGDLYEEEMR_SIL	7.5	2	632.79	574.25	25.1
LGDLYEEEMR_SIL	7.5	2	632.79	703.3	25.1
LGDLYEEEMR_SIL	7.5	2	632.79	866.36	25.1
LHQVYFDAPTCR	6.1	2	502.91	267.13	13.3

LHQVYFDAPTCR	6.1	2	502.91	533.25	13.3
LHQVYFDAPTCR	6.1	2	502.91	604.29	13.3
LHQVYFDAPTCR_SIL	6.1	2	506.25	272.13	13.3
LHQVYFDAPTCR_SIL	6.1	2	506.25	543.26	13.3
LHQVYFDAPTCR_SIL	6.1	2	506.25	614.3	13.3
LINQPLPDLK	7.7	2	575.85	260.2	23.6
LINQPLPDLK	7.7	2	575.85	472.28	23.6
LINQPLPDLK	7.7	2	575.85	682.41	23.6
LINQPLPDLK_SIL	7.7	2	579.85	268.21	23.6
LINQPLPDLK_SIL	7.7	2	579.85	480.29	23.6
LINQPLPDLK_SIL	7.7	2	579.85	690.43	23.6
LISWYDNEFGYSNR	8.4	2	882.405	596.279	16.4
LISWYDNEFGYSNR	8.4	2	882.405	1101.46	16.4
LISWYDNEFGYSNR	8.4	2	882.405	1264.523	16.4
LISWYDNEFGYSNR_SIL	8.4	2	887.409	606.287	16.4
LISWYDNEFGYSNR_SIL	8.4	2	887.409	1111.47	16.4
LISWYDNEFGYSNR_SIL	8.4	2	887.409	1274.53	16.4
LLQTGTEDQGK	3.7	2	595.31	204.13	24.2
LLQTGTEDQGK	3.7	2	595.31	734.33	24.2
LLQTGTEDQGK	3.7	2	595.31	835.38	24.2
LLQTGTEDQGK_SIL	3.7	2	599.31	212.15	24.2
LLQTGTEDQGK_SIL	3.7	2	599.31	742.35	24.2
LLQTGTEDQGK_SIL	3.7	2	599.31	843.39	24.2
LLSETEK	3.4	2	410.23	377.2	18.7
LLSETEK	3.4	2	410.23	593.28	18.7
LLSETEK	3.4	2	410.23	706.36	18.7
LLSETEK_SIL	3.4	2	414.23	385.22	18.7
LLSETEK_SIL	3.4	2	414.23	601.29	18.7
LLSETEK_SIL	3.4	2	414.23	714.38	18.7
LSEGLFTQLR	8.3	2	639.84	517.31	25.5
LSEGLFTQLR	8.3	2	639.84	664.38	25.5
LSEGLFTQLR	8.3	2	639.84	949.51	25.5
LSEGLFTQLR_SIL	8.3	2	644.84	527.32	25.5
LSEGLFTQLR_SIL	8.3	2	644.84	674.39	25.5
LSEGLFTQLR_SIL	8.3	2	644.84	959.52	25.5
LTNSQNFDEYMK	7.1	2	745.34	685.29	28.6
LTNSQNFDEYMK	7.1	2	745.34	832.36	28.6
LTNSQNFDEYMK	7.1	2	745.34	946.4	28.6
LTNSQNFDEYMK_SIL	7.1	2	749.34	693.3	28.6
LTNSQNFDEYMK_SIL	7.1	2	749.34	840.37	28.6
LTNSQNFDEYMK_SIL	7.1	2	749.34	954.41	28.6
LVINGNPITIFQER	8.9	2	807.45	213.16	30.4
LVINGNPITIFQER	8.9	2	807.45	1003.56	30.4

LVINGNPITIFQER	8.9	2	807.45	1288.66	30.4
LVINGNPITIFQER_SIL	8.9	2	812.46	213.16	30.4
LVINGNPITIFQER_SIL	8.9	2	812.46	1013.57	30.4
LVINGNPITIFQER_SIL	8.9	2	812.46	1298.67	30.4
LVPTYESASIR	6.3	2	618.34	512.26	24.8
LVPTYESASIR	6.3	2	618.34	825.41	24.8
LVPTYESASIR	6.3	2	618.34	1023.51	24.8
LVPTYESASIR_SIL	6.3	2	623.34	517.26	24.8
LVPTYESASIR_SIL	6.3	2	623.34	835.42	24.8
LVPTYESASIR_SIL	6.3	2	623.34	1033.52	24.8
MATDPENIIK	6.8	2	566.29	357.21	23.3
MATDPENIIK	6.8	2	566.29	713.42	23.3
MATDPENIIK	6.8	2	566.29	929.49	23.3
MATDPENIIK_SIL	6.8	2	570.3	361.22	23.3
MATDPENIIK_SIL	6.8	2	570.3	721.43	23.3
MATDPENIIK_SIL	6.8	2	570.3	937.51	23.3
MFVLTVAENQVPLAK	8.5	2	865.98	279.12	32.1
MFVLTVAENQVPLAK	8.5	2	865.98	428.29	32.1
MFVLTVAENQVPLAK	8.5	2	865.98	1040.57	32.1
MFVLTVAENQVPLAK_SIL	8.5	2	869.99	279.12	32.1
MFVLTVAENQVPLAK_SIL	8.5	2	869.99	436.3	32.1
MFVLTVAENQVPLAK_SIL	8.5	2	869.99	1048.59	32.1
MHDLNIAMDGLR	7.7	2	462.56	591.29	11.9
MHDLNIAMDGLR	7.7	2	462.56	662.33	11.9
MHDLNIAMDGLR	7.7	2	462.56	724.35	11.9
MHDLNIAMDGLR_SIL	7.7	2	465.9	601.3	11.9
MHDLNIAMDGLR_SIL	7.7	2	465.9	672.34	11.9
MHDLNIAMDGLR_SIL	7.7	2	465.9	724.35	11.9
MSSTFIGNSTAIQELFK	8.7	2	937.47	389.23	34.2
MSSTFIGNSTAIQELFK	8.7	2	937.47	1207.63	34.2
MSSTFIGNSTAIQELFK	8.7	2	937.47	1320.72	34.2
MSSTFIGNSTAIQELFK_SIL	8.7	2	941.48	393.24	34.2
MSSTFIGNSTAIQELFK_SIL	8.7	2	941.48	1215.65	34.2
MSSTFIGNSTAIQELFK_SIL	8.7	2	941.48	1328.73	34.2
QASHAQLGDAYDQEIR	5.3	2	601.29	545.3	16.8
QASHAQLGDAYDQEIR	5.3	2	601.29	660.33	16.8
QASHAQLGDAYDQEIR	5.3	2	601.29	823.39	16.8
QASHAQLGDAYDQEIR_SIL	5.3	2	604.62	555.31	16.8
QASHAQLGDAYDQEIR_SIL	5.3	2	604.62	670.34	16.8
QASHAQLGDAYDQEIR_SIL	5.3	2	604.62	833.4	16.8
SIELESVR	6	2	466.76	490.26	20.4
SIELESVR	6	2	466.76	603.35	20.4
SIELESVR	6	2	466.76	732.39	20.4

SIELESVR_SIL	6	2	471.76	500.27	20.4
SIELESVR_SIL	6	2	471.76	613.35	20.4
SIELESVR_SIL	6	2	471.76	742.4	20.4
SLSDNINLPQGVR	7.8	2	706.88	556.32	27.4
SLSDNINLPQGVR	7.8	2	706.88	669.4	27.4
SLSDNINLPQGVR	7.8	2	706.88	783.45	27.4
SLSDNINLPQGVR_SIL	7.8	2	711.88	566.33	27.4
SLSDNINLPQGVR_SIL	7.8	2	711.88	679.41	27.4
SLSDNINLPQGVR_SIL	7.8	2	711.88	793.46	27.4
SVVSLDGDK	5.1	2	460.24	319.16	20.2
SVVSLDGDK	5.1	2	460.24	634.3	20.2
SVVSLDGDK	5.1	2	460.24	733.37	20.2
SVVSLDGDK_SIL	5.1	2	464.25	327.18	20.2
SVVSLDGDK_SIL	5.1	2	464.25	642.32	20.2
SVVSLDGDK_SIL	5.1	2	464.25	741.39	20.2
THYPDVFAR	5.9	2	553.275	402.177	8.5
THYPDVFAR	5.9	2	553.275	704.37	8.5
THYPDVFAR	5.9	2	553.275	867.44	8.5
THYPDVFAR_SIL	5.9	2	558.279	402.177	8.5
THYPDVFAR_SIL	5.9	2	558.279	714.38	8.5
THYPDVFAR_SIL	5.9	2	558.279	877.44	8.5
TLEIEACR	5.5	2	496.25	535.23	21.3
TLEIEACR	5.5	2	496.25	648.31	21.3
TLEIEACR	5.5	2	496.25	777.36	21.3
TLEIEACR_SIL	5.5	2	501.25	545.24	21.3
TLEIEACR_SIL	5.5	2	501.25	658.32	21.3
TLEIEACR_SIL	5.5	2	501.25	787.36	21.3
TSFTQEQIEALEK	7.9	2	762.38	460.28	29.1
TSFTQEQIEALEK	7.9	2	762.38	589.32	29.1
TSFTQEQIEALEK	7.9	2	762.38	959.5	29.1
TSFTQEQIEALEK_SIL	7.9	2	766.39	468.29	29.1
TSFTQEQIEALEK_SIL	7.9	2	766.39	597.33	29.1
TSFTQEQIEALEK_SIL	7.9	2	766.39	967.52	29.1
VGLNAQAACAPR	4.9	2	614.32	574.28	24.7
VGLNAQAACAPR	4.9	2	614.32	645.31	24.7
VGLNAQAACAPR	4.9	2	614.32	773.37	24.7
VGLNAQAACAPR_SIL	4.9	2	619.32	584.29	24.7
VGLNAQAACAPR_SIL	4.9	2	619.32	655.32	24.7
VGLNAQAACAPR_SIL	4.9	2	619.32	783.38	24.7
VQYESSEPADFK	5.7	2	700.32	294.18	27.2
VQYESSEPADFK	5.7	2	700.32	577.3	27.2
VQYESSEPADFK	5.7	2	700.32	880.41	27.2
VQYESSEPADFK_SIL	5.7	2	704.33	302.2	27.2

VQYESSEPADFK_SIL	5.7	2	704.33	585.31	27.2
VQYESSEPADFK_SIL	5.7	2	704.33	888.42	27.2
YIYTIDGSR	6.7	2	544.28	277.16	22.7
YIYTIDGSR	6.7	2	544.28	648.33	22.7
YIYTIDGSR	6.7	2	544.28	811.39	22.7
YIYTIDGSR_SIL	6.7	2	549.28	277.16	22.7
YIYTIDGSR_SIL	6.7	2	549.28	658.34	22.7
YIYTIDGSR_SIL	6.7	2	549.28	821.4	22.7
YLATASTMDHAR	4.1	2	446.22	277.16	11.3
YLATASTMDHAR	4.1	2	446.22	495.23	11.3
YLATASTMDHAR	4.1	2	446.22	530.75	11.3
YLATASTMDHAR_SIL	4.1	2	449.55	277.16	11.3
YLATASTMDHAR_SIL	4.1	2	449.55	500.23	11.3
YLATASTMDHAR_SIL	4.1	2	449.55	535.75	11.3
YYETGSIRPR	4	2	414.55	393.73	10.1
YYETGSIRPR	4	2	414.55	458.25	10.1
YYETGSIRPR	4	2	414.55	539.79	10.1
YYETGSIRPR_SIL	4	2	417.88	398.74	10.1
YYETGSIRPR_SIL	4	2	417.88	463.26	10.1
YYETGSIRPR_SIL	4	2	417.88	544.79	10.1

Table 4: Vanquish NEO – TSQ Altis Plus method script

{Initial Time}	Instrument Setup	
	UV.Data_Collection_Rate	20.0 [Hz]
	UV.PeakWidth	0.020 [min]
	UV.ResponseTime	0.20 [s]
	Neo.SamplerModule.Sampler.LoadingVolume	Automatic
	Neo.SamplerModule.Sampler.FastLoadingWanted	Yes
	Neo.SamplerModule.Sampler.KeepLoopInline	No
	Neo.SamplerModule.Sampler.DirectLoadingFlow	100.000 [µl/min]
	Neo.SamplerModule.Sampler.DirectLoadingMode	CombinedControl
	Neo.SamplerModule.Sampler.DirectLoadingPressure	1000.0 [bar]
	Neo.SamplerModule.Sampler.TrapZebraWashCycles	4
	Neo.SamplerModule.Sampler.TrapZebraWashWanted	No
	Neo.PumpModule.Pump.FastColumnEquilibrationWanted	Yes
	Neo.PumpModule.Pump.ColumnEquilibrationFactor	3.0
	Neo.PumpModule.Pump.ColumnEquilibrationFlow	100.000 [µl/min]

	Neo.PumpModule.Pump.ColumnEquilibrationMode	CombinedControl
	Neo.PumpModule.Pump.ColumnEquilibrationPressure	1000.0 [bar]
	Neo.PumpModule.Pump.%B.Equate	%B
	Neo.PumpModule.Pump.%A.Equate	%A
	Neo.PumpModule.Pump.%A_Solvent	H2O
	Neo.PumpModule.Pump.%B_Solvent	ACN
	Neo.SamplerModule.Sampler.SolventWeakWpName	Solvent WWP
	Neo.SamplerModule.Sampler.SolventStrongWpName	Solvent SWP
	Neo.SamplerModule.Sampler.SolventWeakName	Solvent W
	Neo.SamplerModule.Sampler.SolventStrongName	Solvent S
	Neo.SamplerModule.TempCtrl	On
	Neo.SamplerModule.Temperature.Nominal	7.0 [°C]
	Neo.SamplerModule.Sampler.PunctureOffset	NoOffset
	Neo.SamplerModule.Sampler.VialBottomDetection	On
	Neo.SamplerModule.Sampler.DispenseSpeed	5.000 [µl/s]
	Neo.SamplerModule.Sampler.DrawDelay	2.0 [s]
	Neo.SamplerModule.Sampler.DrawSpeed	0.200 [µl/s]
	Neo.SamplerModule.Sampler.AirGapEnable	Off
	Neo.SamplerModule.Sampler.OuterNeedleWashCycleTime	Default
	Neo.SamplerModule.Sampler.InjectWashWeakTime	5.0 [s]
	Neo.SamplerModule.Sampler.InjectWashWeakSpeed	80.0 [µl/s]
	Neo.SamplerModule.Sampler.InjectWashStrongSpeed	80.0 [µl/s]
	Neo.SamplerModule.Sampler.InjectWashStrongTime	3.0 [s]
	Neo.SamplerModule.Sampler.InjectWashMode	AfterDraw
	Neo.ColumnCompartmentModule.ColumnChamber.TempCtrl	Off
	Neo.SystemControllerModule.SeparationColumn1.Diameter	150 [µm]
	Neo.SystemControllerModule.SeparationColumn1.Length	15.0 [cm]
	Neo.SystemControllerModule.SeparationColumn1.MaximumPressure	1000 [bar]
	Neo.SystemControllerModule.SeparationColumn1.MaximumFlow	100.0 [µl/min]
	Neo.SystemControllerModule.SeparationColumn1.MaximumTemperature	60.0 [°C]
	Neo.SystemControllerModule.SeparationColumn1.MaximumPressureChangeDown	1000 [bar/min]
	Neo.SystemControllerModule.SeparationColumn1.MaximumPressureChangeUp	1000 [bar/min]
	Neo.SystemControllerModule.InjectionWorkflow	DirectInjection
	Neo.SystemControllerModule.FlowRegime	NanoCap
	Neo.SystemControllerModule.SystemSetup	VanquishNeo
0.000	Equilibration	Duration = 0.000 [min]
	Neo.PumpModule.Pump.Flow.Nominal	1.000 [µl/min]
	Neo.PumpModule.Pump.%B.Value	5.0 [%]
	Neo.PumpModule.Pump.Curve	5
0.000	Inject Preparation	

Neo.SamplerModule.Sampler.Ready And
Neo.PumpModule.Pump.Ready And
Neo.ColumnCompartmentModule.Ready And
Neo.SystemControllerModule.Ready And
MSDevice.Ready

	Wait	
0.000	Inject	
	Neo.SamplerModule.Sampler.Inject	
0.000	Start Run	
	Neo.PumpModule.Pump.Pump_Pressure.AcqOn	
	Neo.SamplerModule.Sampler.Sampler_Pressure.AcqOn	
0.000	Run	Duration = 15.000 [min]
	Neo.PumpModule.Pump.Flow.Nominal	1.000 [µl/min]
	Neo.PumpModule.Pump.%B.Value	5.0 [%]
	Neo.PumpModule.Pump.Curve	5
5.000		
	Neo.PumpModule.Pump.Flow.Nominal	1.000 [µl/min]
	Neo.PumpModule.Pump.%B.Value	15.0 [%]
	Neo.PumpModule.Pump.Curve	5
10.000		
	Neo.PumpModule.Pump.Flow.Nominal	1.000 [µl/min]
	Neo.PumpModule.Pump.%B.Value	50.0 [%]
	Neo.PumpModule.Pump.Curve	5
	Neo.PumpModule.Pump.StartColumnWash	
10.200		
	Neo.PumpModule.Pump.Flow.Nominal	1.000 [µl/min]
	Neo.PumpModule.Pump.%B.Value	95.0 [%]
	Neo.PumpModule.Pump.Curve	5
13.200		
	Neo.PumpModule.Pump.Flow.Nominal	1.000 [µl/min]
	Neo.PumpModule.Pump.%B.Value	95.0 [%]
	Neo.PumpModule.Pump.Curve	5
13.400		
	Neo.PumpModule.Pump.Flow.Nominal	1.000 [µl/min]
	Neo.PumpModule.Pump.%B.Value	5.0 [%]
	Neo.PumpModule.Pump.Curve	5
15.000		
	Neo.PumpModule.Pump.Flow.Nominal	1.000 [µl/min]
	Neo.PumpModule.Pump.%B.Value	5.0 [%]
	Neo.PumpModule.Pump.Curve	5

15.000	Stop Run	
	Neo.PumpModule.Pump.Pump_Pressure.AcqOff	
	Neo.SamplerModule.Sampler.Sampler_Pressure.AcqOff	
15.000	Post Run	Duration = 0.000 [min]
	Neo.PumpModule.Pump.StartColumnEquilibration	
End		